

1 **VALORIZATION OF STEAM-EXPLODED WHEAT STRAW THROUGH A**
2 **BIOREFINERY APPROACH: BIOETHANOL AND BIO-OIL CO-**
3 **PRODUCTION**

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27 **Abstract**

28 The potential of co-producing two different biofuels from a lignocellulosic substrate
29 (wheat straw), according to a biorefinery concept, has been investigated. For such a
30 purpose, simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (SSF) from the hemicellulosic
31 and cellulosic fractions was performed for maximizing bioethanol production. The non-
32 washed water-insoluble solid (WIS) fraction from the pretreated wheat straw totally
33 inhibited the production of ethanol by *Kluyveromyces marxianus* independently of the
34 inoculum size. In contrast, when using washed-WIS, higher ethanol productivities at 24
35 h of SSF were attained when increasing the inoculum size from 1 g/L to 3 g/L. The
36 residual lignin from the bioethanol process was transformed by fast-pyrolysis into bio-oil
37 that can be further converted into other biofuels or biochemicals.

38 Thermal fast-pyrolysis of the residual lignin fraction produced 31.9 wt% of bio-oil*
39 (water free basis) mostly composed by oxygenated aromatics coming from the lignin
40 monomers (guaiacol-, syringol- and phenol-derived compounds). On the other hand,
41 catalytic fast-pyrolysis of the residual lignin fraction over HZSM-5 zeolite was used as
42 preferentially promoted decarbonylation and cracking of the primary vapours.

43 Coupling both processes significantly enhanced the production of liquid products from
44 lignocellulose, improving the efficiency in the use of the raw material. In this way,
45 compared to a simple process of bioethanol production, this approach allowed to increase
46 the mass and the chemical energy yields 1.9 and 1.7-fold, respectively.

47 Keywords: bioethanol; bio-oil; fast-pyrolysis; lignin; biorefinery

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52 **1. Introduction**

53 In future scenario for 2040, the International Energy Agency foresees a continuous world
54 dependence of fossil fuels as energy source, implying a 1/5 increase in CO₂ emissions [1].

55 This fact will provoke, if no preventive measures are taken on time, an increase in the
56 global average temperature of 1.3°C up to 4.0°C by the end of XXI century. The

57 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) considers that with the aim of
58 limiting the temperature increase to 2°C, no more than 1000 Gt of CO₂ can be release

59 from 2014 forward. Therefore, urgent actions should be taken to direct energetic and
60 productive systems towards safe and environmental friendly routes to produce biofuels.

61 In this context, biorefineries have emerged in recent years as attractive alternatives for
62 the co-production of energy and bioproducts with minimum waste generation [2].

63 In order to achieve prices that can be competitive with those of conventional fuels,
64 production cost of biofuels still needs to be reduced. One way to achieve this goal is the

65 use of widely distributed low-cost raw materials. In this context, lignocellulosic sources,
66 widely available as agricultural and forestry wastes, are considered a promising choice.

67 Furthermore, owing to its particular structure, in addition to the well-known process of
68 bioethanol production from carbohydrates, lignocellulosic biomass can be employed to

69 obtain a wide spectrum of chemicals.

70 Among different lignocellulosic raw materials, wheat straw is very suitable for liquid
71 biofuels production [3,4]. The production of 1 kg of wheat grain entails the generarion of

72 1.1 kg of straw [5] and according to the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), 715
73 million tonnes of wheat straw were produced in 2013 worldwide [6]. Taking into account

74 the wheat straw already used for animal feeding and soil maintenance, about 60% of the
75 world production is still available for energy purposes [7].

76 Several studies have already been published proving the effectiveness of using wheat
77 straw for producing bioethanol by means of separate hydrolysis and fermentation (SHF)
78 or simultaneous saccharification and fermentation (SSF) processes [8,9]. Independently
79 of the strategy used, the biomass pretreatment is a crucial step to increase the enzyme
80 accessibility to cellulose and hemicellulose being the steam explosion one of the most
81 widely employed [10]. Steam explosion is based on a hydrothermal reaction in which the
82 biomass is subjected to pressurised steam for a period of time ranging from seconds to
83 several minutes, and then suddenly depressurised. This technology combines mechanical
84 and chemical effects due to the hydrolysis (autohydrolysis) of acetyl groups present in
85 hemicellulose. Steam explosion process shows some advantageous features when
86 compared to other pretreatment methods. These include the significantly lower
87 environmental impact, higher energy efficiency, possibility of using high chip size,
88 unnecessary addition of acid catalyst (except for softwoods), high sugar recovery and
89 high hydrolysis yields in the following enzymatic hydrolysis [10]. However, the main
90 drawbacks encountered during steam explosion are the partial hemicellulose and lignin
91 degradation which leads to the formation of inhibitory compounds that affect negatively
92 enzymes and microorganisms. Major inhibitors are furan derivatives, mainly 5-
93 hydroxymethyl furfural (HMF) and furfural, weak acids and phenolic compounds. These
94 soluble inhibitors are present in the liquid fraction of the steam-explosion pretreated
95 material together with most of the xylose and thus, their separation by filtration is an
96 straightforward method to diminish their negative effect. In a lignocellulosic biorefinery,
97 this liquid fraction has been proposed to be employed to obtain biopolymers or bioplastics
98 by means of different microorganisms [11,12].
99 *Kluyveromyces marxianus* strains have lately appeared as promising fermenting
100 microorganisms for bioethanol production [13,14]. *K. marxianus* is a thermotolerant yeast

101 that can ferment sugars at temperatures close to the optimum for enzymes which implies
102 higher hydrolysis yields and consequently, higher ethanol concentration in the SSF.
103 Furthermore, the use of thermotolerant yeasts in SSF leads to other advantages such as
104 the reduction of cooling costs and contamination risks, as well as the continuous ethanol
105 removal [15]. Among all possible strategies for producing ethanol from wheat straw, SSF
106 processes with *K. marxianus* have shown very promising results, reaching ethanol yields
107 up to 0.40 g/g [16].

108 With the current emphasis of lignocellulosic bioethanol, increasing reserves of lignin are
109 expected to be available in short-medium term as a by-product of this process [17]. Due
110 to the polyaromatic structure of lignin, this by-product appears as an interesting
111 alternative resource for aromatic chemicals and building-blocks such as phenols, but also
112 as raw material for the production of advanced fuels and additives [18,19]. Nevertheless,
113 hardly 2 % of the produced lignin is commercially used nowadays for low-value products
114 such as dispersing or binding agents while the rest is used as energy source for direct
115 combustion [20].

116 In this sense, the conversion of lignin into biofuels/biochemicals via thermal and catalytic
117 fast-pyrolysis is envisaged as a promising approach [18,21,22]. Lignin, however, is more
118 difficult to be depolymerized and produces more residual char than cellulose and
119 hemicellulose [21,23,24]. Several works have been dealt the valorization of lignin
120 through fast-pyrolysis [18,23,25]. Some of them are related to simple thermal processes
121 [26,27], while others refer to catalytic fast-pyrolysis [18,21–23,26,28–30]. In this way,
122 different zeolites, such as HZSM-5 [18,21,22,28–30], have been shown very effective
123 catalysts in the pyrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass, allowing the removal of oxygen from
124 the thermal bio-oil through three deoxygenation pathways: decarbonylation (CO),
125 decarboxylation (CO₂) and dehydration (H₂O).

126 There are a few examples in the literature related to the valorisation of the residual
127 products after the bioethanol process. Lignin recovered after ethanol production from
128 corn stover and rice straw was used for pyrolytic production of phenolic compounds [31].
129 On the other hand, residuals from starch-based ethanol production were used to produce
130 bio-oil by catalytic liquefaction [32]. However, to our knowledge, this is the first time
131 that lignin residue from steam-pretreated wheat straw is studied to co-produce an
132 alternative liquid biofuel (i.e. bio-oil).

133 In the present work, *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 has been used to produce bioethanol from
134 the water-insoluble solid (WIS) fraction of pretreated wheat straw. The effects of
135 implementing a washing process to remove the inhibitors and increasing the inoculum
136 sizes are studied for maximizing the bioethanol production. On the other hand, the
137 residual lignin has been studied as raw material for thermal and catalytic (over HZSM-5
138 zeolite) fast-pyrolysis.

139 Overall, this work was devoted to demonstrate and quantify, based on experimental data,
140 the benefits of co-producing two different liquid biofuels (bioethanol and bio-oil) from
141 lignocellulose combining fermentative and pyrolysis processes, following the so-called
142 biorefinery concept.

143 **2. Materials and Methods**

144 *2.1. Biomass source and pretreatment*

145 Wheat straw (WS) was provided by CEDER-CIEMAT (Soria, Spain). This material had
146 the following composition (wt%, dry basis): cellulose, 40.5; hemicelluloses, 26.1 (xylan,
147 22.7; arabinan, 2.1; and galactan, 1.3); Klason lignin, 18.1; ash, 5.1; and extractives, 14.6
148 [33]. The raw material was milled using a laboratory hammer mill (Restch) and sieved to
149 obtain a particle size between 2 and 10 mm, being stored until use. The particle size was
150 chosen according to previous studies [9].

151 WS was pretreated in a steam explosion pilot plant without acid impregnation.
152 Temperature and residence time were set at 200°C and 10 min, respectively. Under these
153 conditions heating up time ranged from 45 to 60 sec and after depressurization, 30 sec
154 were enough to reduce the temperature down to 100°C. After pretreatment, the obtained
155 slurry was vacuum filtered in order to obtain two fractions: (i) the water-insoluble solids
156 (WIS) fraction and (ii) the prehydrolysate or liquid fraction. Both fractions, which
157 represented 71.1 wt% and 22.4 wt%, respectively, of the WS, were analysed as described
158 in analytical methods and their compositions are shown in Table 1. The remaining 6.5
159 wt% corresponded to mass losses in form of volatile compounds during pretreatment and
160 during the recovery process because of the material handling. In order to remove all the
161 inhibitors soaked in the material, a part of the WIS fraction was thoroughly washed with
162 distilled water before use. After the removal of cellulosic and hemicellulosic fractions,
163 the lignin fraction (LIG) was used for bio-oil production by thermal and catalytic fast-
164 pyrolysis.

165 2.2. Catalyst (zeolite HZSM-5)

166 For catalytic fast-pyrolysis test, HZSM-5 zeolite supplied by CLARIANT was employed.
167 The amount of aluminium of this sample was determined by ICP-OES, showing a Si/Al
168 molar ratio of 42. Argon physisorption isotherms at -186°C were measured on a
169 AUTOSORB iQ system (Quantachrome). The surface area was determined using the
170 Brunauer–Emmet–Teller (BET) equation and the pore size distributions were calculated
171 by applying the NLDFT model to the adsorption branch of the isotherm. The specific
172 surface area and micropore volume showed values of 347 m²/g and 0.134 cm³/g,
173 respectively. The acidity of the zeolite was measured by temperature programmed
174 desorption (TPD) of NH₃ using an AUTOCHEM 2910 system (Micromeritics). The
175 procedure applied for the TPD measurements was previously described [34]. The HZSM-

176 5 sample presented an acidity of 0.414 mmol NH₃ g⁻¹, which was in agreement with its
177 Al content (Si/Al = 42). The TPD curve exhibited two desorption peaks, one at about
178 165°C associated with weak acidic sites, and a broader, less intense feature at 335°C,
179 which was attributed to strong acid sites.

180 Previous to the pyrolysis tests, the zeolite sample was pelletized, crushed and sieved to
181 the desired particle size of 180-250 µm.

182 *2.3. Microorganism and growth conditions*

183 *K. marxianus* CECT 10875, selected due to its thermotolerance and high ethanol
184 production [35], was used as fermenting microorganism. Precultures were grown in 100
185 mL shake flasks with YPD media (20 g/L glucose) at 42°C and 130 rpm for 24 h.
186 Thereafter, cultures were centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 8 min. The supernatants were
187 discarded and cell pellets were diluted with sterile MilliQ water to get the appropriate
188 inoculum size in the SSF.

189 *2.4. Simultaneous saccharification and fermentation*

190 Non-washed WIS at 10 wt% and washed WIS fractions at 10 or 12 wt% of substrate
191 loading were used in SSF experiments. WIS was diluted in citrate buffer 50 mM pH 5.0
192 with 5 g/L yeast extract, 2 g/L NH₄Cl, 1 g/L KH₂PO₄ y 0.3 g/L MgSO₄·7H₂O. The
193 hydrolytic enzymes employed were NS50013 (Celluclast 1.5L, 60 FPU/mL) and
194 NS50010 (Novozyme 188, 800 CBU/mL), kindly supplied by Novozymes. Enzyme
195 loading was fixed at 10 FPU/g cellulose and 10 CBU/g cellulose for NS50013 and
196 NS50010, respectively. SSF were performed in triplicate in 100 mL shake flasks with 25
197 mL working volume at 140 rpm and 42°C for 144 h. Shake flasks were inoculated with 1
198 or 3 g/L dry weight of cells depending on the assay conditions. Samples were withdrawn
199 periodically for sugars and ethanol analyses.

200 *2.5. Obtention of the lignin residue*

201 A complete enzymatic hydrolysis of the WIS fraction used in the SSF assays (15 FPU/g
202 cellulose and 10 CBU/g cellulose for NS50013 and NS50010, respectively) was carried
203 out in order to get a LIG free of cellulosic and hemicellulosic fractions. Thereby,
204 enzymatic hydrolysis was performed at 50°C for 144 h; after which, the broth was
205 centrifuged at 8000 g for 5 min, thoroughly washed with distilled water and centrifuged
206 again. The remaining residue was oven dried at 105°C overnight and kept in a refrigerator.
207 The humidity after the drying process was 11.1 wt%.

208 *2.6. Fast-pyrolysis tests*

209 Fast-pyrolysis experiments of LIG were carried out in a lab-scale experimental setup
210 consisting of a downdraft fixed-bed stainless steel reactor [36]. LIG sample (5 g) was
211 placed in the biomass tank at room temperature. To avoid the physical contact and
212 possible mixing between catalyst and biomass, a quartz wool sheet and a metallic plate
213 were placed over the catalyst particles (in case of catalytic test). The pyrolysis tests were
214 carried out at 500°C and atmospheric pressure. Once the reactor temperature reached the
215 desired set point, the feeding valve was opened and LIG fell in the reactor. The generated
216 volatiles, pushed by a N₂ flow of 100 NmL/min, passed through the catalyst bed (in case
217 of the catalytic tests) to leave rapidly the reaction zone and recovered by a condensation
218 system with an ice-water trap (0-4°C); while permanent gases and light hydrocarbons
219 were collected in a sampling bag for further analysis. The gas mass yield and its elemental
220 analysis in terms of C, H and O were calculated from the gas composition at the exit of
221 the reactor.

222 After the experiments, the char and the used catalyst were collected for further analysis.
223 Char was characterized in the same way as the LIG, proximate and ultimate analyses
224 being performed. In the case of the coke fraction, the produced amount was determined
225 as the weight loss experienced by the spent catalyst in TGA tests with a heating program

226 of 20°C/min up to 550°C in air atmosphere. Similarly to LIG and char samples, elemental
227 analysis of coke was also conducted. Finally, from the weight of the bio-oil and char
228 fractions and those calculated for coke and gas fractions, the total mass balance was
229 closed to the amount of LIG fed.

230 *2.7. Analytical methods*

231 The proximate analysis of the WS and LIG samples was assessed according to European
232 standards. The moisture, ash and volatile matter contents were determined according to
233 UNE-EN 14774-1:2010, UNE-EN 14775:2010 and UNE-EN 15148:2010, respectively;
234 whereas the fixed carbon was calculated by difference. The ultimate analysis of WS and
235 LIG samples were carried out in a micro-elemental analyser to determine the content of
236 C, H, N, S and O (by difference). Moreover, a correlation valid for solid, liquid and
237 gaseous fuels was used to calculate the WS and LIG high heating values (HHV) [37].

238 The chemical composition of the WIS fraction and slurry was analyzed using the National
239 Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) standard methods for determination of structural
240 carbohydrates and lignin in biomass (LAP-002, LAP- 003, and LAP-019). Sugars,
241 phenols and degradation compounds contained in the prehydrolysate were determined
242 and quantified by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) in an Agilent 1260
243 chromatograph (Agilent, Waldbronn, Germany), as explained elsewhere [38]. Sugars and
244 ethanol concentrations along the SSF were also analysed by HPLC with the same column,
245 detector and mobile phase stated before but with flow rate of 0.6 mL/min.

246 Two phases were distinguished in the obtained bio-oils. In this manner, both phases were
247 manually separated after centrifugation for an accurate analysis. The water content was
248 determined using a Karl-Fischer titration (ASTM E203-08), whilst the elemental
249 composition of C, H, N, S and O (by difference) was performed with a Thermo-Scientific
250 micro analyser. The bio-oil fraction in water free basis was named as Bio-oil*. Gas

251 Chromatograph Mass Spectrometer (GC-MS) was used to analyse the bio-oils
252 composition. NIST EI-MS spectral library (v2.0) was used for compounds identification
253 (with a minimum match score of 700). Bio-oil compounds were further grouped in
254 families according to main functional groups. Permanent gases (H_2 , N_2 , CO and CO_2) and
255 light hydrocarbons (CH_4 , C_2H_4 , C_2H_6 , C_3H_6 and C_3H_8), collected in a sampling bag, were
256 analysed in a Micro Gas Chromatograph (Micro-GC).

257 *2.8. Calculations (mass and energy balances)*

258 The theoretical ethanol was calculated taking into account the glucose present in the WIS
259 fraction and assuming the maximum stoichiometrical conversion of glucose into ethanol
260 (0.51 g ethanol/g glucose). Similarly, the experimental ethanol yield was determined
261 taking into account the WIS yield (from the steam explosion pretreatment) and its glucose
262 content, assuming the experimental conversion of glucose into ethanol.

263 LIG yield was calculated from the remaining fraction after the SSF process; which
264 consists on lignin and residual amounts of hemicellulose and glucose (see Table 1).

265 When fast-pyrolysis of LIG was considered in the biorefinery approach, the bio-oil yield
266 was calculated as the amount of bio-oil produced (in water free basis) per gram of WS
267 fed. The same calculation was used for the mass yield of the rest of the pyrolysis products.

268 The energy yield of these products was estimated from their mass yield and their heating
269 value (MJ/kg) with respect to the WS heating value.

270 **3. Results and discussion**

271 In this work, the co-production of two biofuels from a lignocellulosic substrate (wheat
272 straw) has been combined according to a biorefinery approach (scheme shown in Figure
273 1). The process starts with the steam explosion pretreatment of lignocellulose after which
274 the WIS fraction and the prehydrolysate were obtained. WIS is used for bioethanol
275 production, whilst the residual lignin is subjected to thermal/catalytic fast-pyrolysis to

276 obtain a liquid fraction (bio-oil) that could be employed for the production of
277 biochemicals and/or biofuels. Moreover, it is proposed an integrated scheme in which the
278 heat obtained from the combustion of the char and gas fractions could be employed to
279 supply the energy required in the different stages of the process, such as the steam
280 explosion pretreatment, the residual lignin drying or even the pyrolysis process itself.

281 *3.1. Wheat straw and lignin analysis*

282 Table 2 shows proximate and ultimate analyses of the WS and LIG. It is observed that
283 LIG hardly presented 54 wt% of volatile matter, which was a relatively low value for a
284 potential pyrolysis raw material, especially when compared to that of WS (81.1 wt%).
285 This was expected since the cellulose and hemicellulose removal results in a lignin solid
286 residue enriched in fixed carbon and high ash content.

287 The thermal behaviours under inert atmosphere of both raw WS and LIG samples are
288 shown in Figure 2. It can be observed that WS did not only loose more weight, but also
289 the polysaccharides comprising the holocellulose material were much more reactive than
290 lignin. On the other hand, by deconvolution of the WS DTG curve, three peaks
291 corresponding to hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin, respectively, were identified [39–
292 42]. In this case, hemicellulose decomposed at 200-375°C, which presents a maximum
293 DTG value at 289°C; cellulose (280-390°C), which presents a maximum DTG value at
294 334°C; and lignin (150-600°C). In contrast, the DTG curve of LIG only showed two peaks
295 after deconvolution; the remaining holocellulose material (280-360°C) with a maximum
296 DTG value at 325°C and the lignin fraction (150-600°C). The relative proportions of the
297 area of these peaks in LIG were 14.6 and 85.4 wt%, respectively. These data denoted that
298 this material contained a small but still significant amount of holocellulose. Table 2 shows
299 that LIG contained almost 29 % less oxygen than WS, but it was still relatively high (\approx
300 32 wt%). Thus, the HHV of LIG was hardly 13 % higher than that of its precursor. This

301 fact evidenced the benefit of the proposed alternative valorization such as the bio-oil
302 production via fast-pyrolysis, instead of LIG burning..

303 3.2. SSF experiments with non-washed WIS fraction

304 Figure 3 shows the results of SSF experiments using non-washed WIS at 10 wt% with 1
305 or 3 g/L inoculum size. When the experiment was performed with 1 g/L of inoculum size
306 (Figure 3a), cells were totally inhibited and no ethanol was produced. However, glucose
307 concentration reached 29.5 ± 0.3 g/L at 144 h, corresponding to 53 % of the maximum
308 glucose hydrolysis yield. When increasing the inoculum size to 3 g/L the maximum
309 ethanol concentration was 4.2 ± 0.2 g/L, which implied 15-% of the maximum theoretical
310 ethanol (Figure 3b). The higher ethanol concentration obtained with 3 g/L of inoculum,
311 compared with 1 g/L, also gave rise to a lower glucose concentration remaining at the end
312 of the process (24.9 ± 1.4 g/L).

313 The inhibition of the ethanol production process when using the non-washed WIS may
314 be due to the presence of inhibitors that remained soaked in the material. The same *K.*
315 *marxianus* CECT 10875 strain has been previously used in SSF experiments from WS
316 using the whole slurry or non-washed WIS at similar substrate loading (10 wt%). In other
317 studies, acetic and formic acid concentrations were 6.4 g/L and 2.6 g/L, respectively [14]
318 or 6.9 g/L and 6.3 g/L [16], Nevertheless, in the present study with a pretreatment at
319 200°C and 10 min, acetic acid concentration was 13.3 g/L and formic acid concentration
320 was 9.5 g/L. Acetic acid is produced from the acetyl groups in hemicelluloses, whereas
321 formic acid derives from furfural and HMF degradation [43]. The undissociated form of
322 the weak acids can diffuse across the cell membrane and dissociate inside the cell due to
323 the higher intracellular pH. This fact decreases intracellular pH which is compensated by
324 pumping protons out of the cell at the expense of ATP. Thus, less ATP is available for
325 biomass formation. Furthermore, if pumping capacity of the plasma membrane ATPase

326 is overcome, acidification of cytoplasm and cellular death occur [44]. Likewise, the
327 negative effect of these acids on thermotolerant yeast could be even higher due to the
328 effect that high temperatures cause on the fluidification of cell membranes. It has been
329 previously reported that when increasing the process temperature from 40 to 44°C, a
330 negative effect on *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 viability was observed even in absence of
331 inhibitors [45]. Both facts, would explain the sub-optimal performance of *K. marxianus*
332 CECT 10875 in non-washed WIS.

333 3.3. SSF experiments with washed WIS fraction

334 The non-washed WIS was thoroughly washed with distilled water to completely remove
335 the soluble inhibitors that were soaked in the material. As it can be observed in Table 3,
336 18.8±0.7 g/L and 21.1±1.9 g/L of ethanol were obtained with 1 g/L and 3 g/L of
337 inoculum size, respectively, from 10 wt% washed WIS. Therefore, the washing treatment
338 made fermentable 10 wt% of WIS that was non-fermentable before the washing (Figure
339 2).

340 In order to increase the amount of potentially fermentable sugars, SSF was also performed
341 at 12 wt% of washed WIS. When increasing the substrate loading, even smaller
342 differences were observed in terms of maximum ethanol concentration between the SSF
343 with 1 g/L and 3 g/L of inoculum size (Table 3). Ethanol concentrations obtained with 12
344 wt% were no significantly higher than those achieved with 10 wt%. Moreover, since the
345 amount of potentially fermentable glucose was higher when using 12 wt% WIS, the
346 percentage of the theoretical maximum ethanol was lower when compared to 10 wt%
347 substrate loading (Table 3).

348 Ethanol productivities at 24 h (Q_{24}) increased from 0.51 to 0.60 and from 0.33 to 0.73
349 with 10 and 12 wt% substrate loadings, respectively, by increasing the inoculum size to
350 3 g/L. In spite of the higher potentially available sugar, the ethanol productivity at 24 h

351 with 12 wt% and 1 g/L was lower than the one obtained at 10 wt% with the same inoculum
352 size. It is known that even if the material is previously washed, some inhibitory
353 compounds can be released during the enzymatic hydrolysis step [33,46]. In this case,
354 when using the lower inoculum size (1 g/L) at higher substrate loading, cells need more
355 time to cope with the inhibitors released during the hydrolysis and enlarge the lag phase
356 to adapt to the changing conditions. In principle, the longer is the lag phase, the lower
357 ethanol volumetric productivities would be attained. This effect was not observed when
358 using 3 g/L since the higher inoculum size was enough to overcome the inhibitory effect
359 of the released degradation compounds.

360 Increasing the inoculum size, however, did not have a marked effect on maximum ethanol
361 production in a 144 h-long SSF. This fact could be due to the lower cell viability after
362 exposing the cells at high temperature for long periods of time.

363 In summary, 73 % of the maximum ethanol concentration was obtained under the best
364 conditions assayed. Furthermore, the effectiveness of the washing process to remove the
365 inhibitors was proven by rendering the material more easily fermentable.

366 *3.4. Bio-oil production from LIG via fast-pyrolysis: thermal vs. catalytic*

367 LIG was subjected to both thermal and catalytic fast-pyrolysis at 500°C and atmospheric
368 pressure in a lab-scale reactor. Table 4 reports the mass yield distribution of the pyrolysis
369 products as well as some bio-oil* parameters.

370 Regarding the liquid fraction, and depending on the water content and on the type and
371 polarity of the organic components present, a phase separation may occur; and thus, bio-
372 oil often consists of two phases: aqueous and organic. In the current work, the organic
373 phase represented most of the bio-oil weight, accounting for 83.9 and 73.7 wt% of the
374 thermal and catalytic bio-oils, respectively. Moreover, water was detected in both liquid
375 phases. This fact evidenced that a liquid-liquid equilibrium was established rather than a

376 total segregation of the different components. However, the water content in those phases
377 was very different with values of 58 and 87 wt% (aqueous phase) and 13 and 4 wt%
378 (organic phase) for the thermal and catalytic bio-oils, respectively.

379 It can be observed that catalytic fast-pyrolysis produced less bio-oil* in comparison with
380 the purely thermal test. This fact is originated by the formation of more gases and water,
381 as well as of some coke deposited over the catalyst surface. The variation in the
382 production of water and of the different gas components provides direct insights about
383 the deoxygenation routes that are favoured by the zeolite catalyst. Thus, the CO, CO₂ and
384 H₂O production increased by 46.5, 8.4 and 10.8 %, respectively, in the catalytic test with
385 respect to the thermal one. These results denoted that HZSM-5 zeolite preferentially
386 promoted the decarbonylation route, which was not really very positive in terms of mass
387 and energy yields of the bio-oil* fraction. Formation of CO is detrimental as it involves
388 a loss of both carbon and chemical energy. In addition, the zeolite catalyst showed a
389 noteworthy cracking activity due to its strong acidic properties. Accordingly, olefins
390 concentration was six fold higher than in the thermal experient. Likewise, the coke formed
391 over the catalyst consisted of carbonaceous that represented 1.9 wt% of the LIG fed. It
392 has been proposed that this coke is originated from partial deoxygenation of the lignin
393 aromatic units producing simple phenols, which can undergo repolymerization [21,23],
394 as well as by the formation of polyaromatics hydrocarbons (PAHs) [47–49]. Coke
395 deposits represented 3.7 % of the LIG energy yield, due to its high carbon content (78.4
396 wt%).

397 On the other hand, char is also an important by-product of the pyrolysis process as it
398 contains a significant proportion of the chemical energy present in the feeding material.
399 The minimum char yield, in dry basis, should be at least equal to the sum of the fixed
400 carbon and ash contents of the lignin fed (46.1 wt%). In case of catalytic pyrolysis, the

401 catalyst bed was set up in such a manner that there was no direct contact between zeolite
402 and LIG during pyrolysis. Therefore, the catalyst presence did not affect the primary
403 decomposition of lignin neither the formation of char. For that reason, similar char yields
404 (around 46 wt%) were obtained in both thermal and catalytic pyrolysis tests. The
405 importance of this by-product relies on its high carbon content (Table 2), since it retained
406 around 60 wt% of the carbon initially present in LIG, whereas it contained just 7.7 wt%
407 of oxygen. This was directly linked to the energy yield, the char fraction representing
408 around 57 % of the LIG chemical energy. Since the pyrolysis process itself would require
409 about 15 % of the biomass energy, this heat could be supplied by burning the char to make
410 the pyrolysis process energy self-sufficient [50]. Moreover, the excess of heat obtained
411 from char combustion could be used for the WS steam explosion pretreatment and/or for
412 the residual lignin drying.

413 In summary, the results obtained indicate that, at least in the conditions here employed
414 and with this type of strong acidic catalyst, the catalytic pyrolysis of the LIG fraction did
415 not provide any significant advantage compared to the pure thermal conversion, since it
416 did not improve the bio-oil* composition (in terms of reducing the oxygen content) nor
417 the bio-oil* yield. Consequently, for this route to be an interesting option, the operation
418 conditions (temperature and catalyst/biomass ratio) and/or the catalyst properties (such
419 as acidity, etc.) should be further optimized to promote decarboxylation and dehydration
420 as main deoxygenation pathways and to reduce the important mass and energy losses
421 associated with the formation of coke and olefins.

422 Focusing on the non-catalytic pyrolysis test, Figure 4a shows the bio-oil composition
423 determined by GC-MS analysis. Thereby, aqueous and organic phases of the bio-oil were
424 separately analysed to determine the distribution of compound families in both phases.
425 The identified compounds were classified into seven groups: carboxylic acids (AC),

426 alcohols (ALC), ketones and ethers (KET & ETH), furans (FUR), sugars (SUG) and
427 oxygenated aromatics (O-AR). The appearance of FUR and SUG confirmed that some
428 rests of holocellulose polymers were still present in LIG. Thus, Figure 4b-d plots display
429 the main components of the ketones and ethers (such as 2,2-Dimethoxypropane and
430 diacetone alcohol, respectively), acids (mostly acetic acid) and furans (mostly 2,3
431 dihydrobenzofuran) families in the thermally obtained bio-oil; which, apart from rests
432 of holocellulose, were also originated from LIG thermal degradation [51]. Nevertheless,
433 the bio-oil was mostly composed by oxygenated aromatics (71.6 % of the total area in the
434 GC-MS analyses). Those components were mainly derived from the three lignin
435 containing monomers or monolignols. Lignin has been described as a random, three-
436 dimensional network polymer comprised of various linked phenylpropane units, derived
437 from three monomers p-hydroxyphenyl (H), guaiacyl (G) and syringyl (S) units
438 differently distributed depending on the raw biomass (softwood, hardwood or grass) [17].
439 Due to their high thermal resistance, those monomers, are expected to maintain their
440 structural identity during the pyrolysis process, giving rise to phenol-, guaiacol- and
441 syringol- substituted compounds, respectively [52]. In this way, the substituted H/G/S
442 ratio were determined from the analyses of the thermal pyrolysis products (Figure 4e),
443 leading to 15.1/57.3/27.6 values. In agreement with previous results from WS, guaiacol-
444 followed by syringol- derived molecules were the principal compounds of the primary
445 organic vapours derived from lignin[53].

446 *3.5. Biorefinery approach: Bioethanol and Bio-oil co-production*

447 This section discusses the advantages of the co-production of bioethanol and bio-oil from
448 WS using the LIG, obtained from the bioethanol production, as raw material for thermal
449 fast-pyrolysis. Mass and energy yields of the co-production process were compared with
450 those obtained for bioethanol in Figure 5. This calculation was based on the data attained

451 for 10 wt% of substrate loading and 3 g/L of inoculum size and that the LIG was
452 decomposed by non-catalytic fast-pyrolysis.

453 When the SSF was the only process being applied, the bioethanol yield was 15.0 wt%,
454 expressed as kg of bioethanol per 100 kg of raw WS. When the fast-pyrolysis of LIG was
455 also considered, bio-oil was obtained as an additional fraction. In this case, the overall
456 mass yield into liquid biofuels (considering only the organic part of the bio-oil, i.e. in a
457 water-free basis) would be almost two-fold higher (up to 28.8 wt%) than only producing
458 bioethanol.

459 In terms of energy yield, the production of bioethanol led to a 24.5 % recovery of the
460 chemical energy initially contained in WS, whereas by adding the direct combustion of
461 LIG more than 49 % of the WS heating value could be attained. In contrast, when
462 combining both treatments (fermentation and fast-pyrolysis), the energy yield
463 corresponding to the liquid biofuels would reach a value around 43 %. In addition, the
464 overall energy efficiency could be further increased if the pyrolysis by-products, gas and
465 solid fractions, are combusted to provide the heat demanded in the different treatments of
466 the whole process, such as steam explosion, WIS drying or pyrolysis itself. In particular,
467 the char fraction is especially interesting for this purpose taking into account both the
468 high amount of char generated by LIG pyrolysis and its good quality as fuel due to its
469 relatively low oxygen content.

470 Overall, this analysis confirmed that the co-production of bioethanol and bio-oil was an
471 advantageous option for lignocellulose valorisation as it could result in remarkable
472 improvements in terms of mass and energy yields. The proposed approach allowed
473 increasing the mass and the chemical energy yields by 1.9 and 1.7-fold, respectively.

474 **4. Conclusions**

475 The co-production of bioethanol and bio-oil from steam exploded wheat straw was shown
476 as an effective manner of maximizing the mass and energy yields into liquid biofuels.

477 The fermentability of WIS fraction when using *K. marxianus* CECT 10875 in SSF
478 processes was increased by applying a previous washing treatment. Moreover, the
479 increase in the inoculum size was crucial to enhance ethanol productivities in spite of not
480 having significant effects on final ethanol concentrations.

481 The use of HZSM-5 zeolite in residual lignin catalytic pyrolysis did not have a positive
482 effect since it reduced the bio-oil* yield while oxygen content was barely decreased.
483 Decarbonylation was the preferred deoxygenation pathway promoted by this catalyst,
484 whereas cracking reactions, leading to gaseous products and coke formation also occurred
485 in the catalytic test.

486 Compared to a simple process of ethanol production, this approach allowed the mass and
487 the chemical energy yields into liquid biofuels to be increased 1.9 and 1.7-fold,
488 respectively. Moreover, it was proposed that some of the secondary products obtained by
489 fast-pyrolysis (gases, coke and mainly the char fraction) could be combusted for
490 providing most of the heat demand in the different steps of the overall process, increasing
491 further its energy efficiency.

492

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664 Table 1. Composition of the pre-treated wheat straw.

WIS		Prehydrolysate			
Component	wt%	Monosaccharides	g/L	Inhibitors	g/L
Glucose	55.5±1.3	Glucose	3.7	Acetic acid	13.3
Xylose	5.4±0.4	Xylose	12.9	Formic acid	9.5
Galactose	0.19±0.0	Galactose	1.3	HMF	0.3
Arabinose	0.27±0.06	Arabinose	0.9	Furfural	0.5
Mannose	0.17±0.02	Mannose	0.7	Vanillin	0.053
Lignin	35.6±0.7			Syringaldehyde	0.026
Ash	5.3±0.06			Coumaric acid	0.003

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667 Table 2. Proximate and ultimate analysis of WS and lignin LIG samples

Sample	Moisture (wt%)	Proximate Analysis, db (wt%)			Ultimate Analysis, db (wt%)				HHV ⁺ (MJ/kg)
		Ash	Vol. Matter	Fixed Carbon	C	H	N	O	
WS	9.4	3.1	81.1	15.8	46.1	5.7	0.6	44.5	18.2
LIG	11.1	10.9	53.9	35.7	51.0	5.4	1.0	31.8	20.6
Char	1.1	23.5	15.5	61.0	66.5	2.8	2.0	5.3	25.4

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db: dry basis

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⁺HHV: high heating value (MJ/kg_{sample})

670 Table 3. Ethanol yield and productivity attained in SSF processes at different conditions

Substrate loading (wt%)	10	12	10	12
Inoculum size (g/L)	1		3	
Potential glucose (g/L) in SSF	55.5	66.6	55.5	66.6
Max Ethanol (g/L)	18.8±0.7	21.3±1.1	21.1±1.2	20.3±0.5
Y _{ETOH/G} (g/g)	0.34	0.32	0.38	0.30
% of the theoretical max ethanol	66.4	62.7	73.1	59.7
Q _{24h} (g/Lh)	0.51	0.33	0.60	0.73

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673 Table 2. Product yield distribution for non-catalytic and catalytic fast-pyrolysis of LIG

Mass yield (wt%)										
	Coke	Gas					H ₂ O	Bio-oil*		
		H ₂	(C ₁ -C ₃) _p	(C ₂ -C ₃) _o	CO	CO ₂		Total	O conc. (wt%)	HHV (MJ/kg _{bio-oil} [*])
Thermal	0.0	0.005	0.70	0.15	2.18	10.45	8.3	31.9	41.2	23.9
Catalytic (ZSM-5)	1.9	0.007	0.83	0.87	3.19	11.33	9.2	26.3	41.5	24.1

674 (C₁-C₃)_p: Paraffins

675 (C₂-C₃)_o: Olefins

676 * Bio-oil water free basis

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679 **Figure legend**

680 Figure 1. Biorefinery concept based on the integration of biological and thermal
681 processing of biomass for transport fuels and chemicals

682 Figure 2. Weight loss and DTG curves for WS (A) and LIG (B) samples. Blue:
683 experimental weight loss curve; Red: experimental DTG curve; Green dash-dot:
684 calculated peaks from the DTG deconvolution computation with Origin software; and
685 Black dash: Simulated DTG curves with Origin software.

686 Figure 3. SSF experiments with non-washed WIS at 10 wt% with 1 or 3 g/L of inoculum
687 size, a) and b) respectively.

688 Figure 4. Bio-oil composition (expressed as % of relative area) obtained by thermal fast-
689 pyrolysis of LIG at 500°C and atmospheric pressure. (A): Main families of compounds;
690 (B): main Ketones and Ethers; (C): Acids; (D): Furans and (E): O-aromatics compounds.

691 Figure 5. Comparison, in terms of mass (A) and energy (B) yield, of the liquid biofuels
692 production (green bars): bioethanol via simultaneous saccharification and fermentation
693 (SSF), coupled to the bio-oil production through the fast-pyrolysis of lignin residue (LIG).

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4

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Figure 5